

BERGISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WUPPERTAL

Bundesministerium
für Forschung, Technologie
und Raumfahrt

PIERRE
AUGER
OBSERVATORY

PROBING THE EXTREME UNIVERSE: SEARCHES FOR NEUTRINOS AND BSM SIGNATURES WITH THE PIERRE AUGER OBSERVATORY

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SRIJAN SEHGAL

FOR THE PIERRE AUGER COLLABORATION

NUPHYS:2026

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- ▶ Largest cosmic ray detector ~3000 km²
- ▶ Surface Detector (SD)
 - ▶ 1660 water Cherenkov stations
 - ▶ Detects EAS via secondary particles at ground
- ▶ Fluorescence Detector (FD)
 - ▶ 4 sites with 27 telescopes
 - ▶ Measures longitude development via fluorescence
- ▶ Duty Cycle - SD ~100%, FD ~15%

- ▶ Deployed AugerPrime upgrade

- ▶ Increases composition sensitivity
- ▶ Potential for increasing neutrino sensitivity
- ▶ More info in :

[PoS\(ICRC2025\)385](#)

[Pierre Auger Coll., NIM A 798 (2015) 172]

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- ▶ UHECR main background, higher separation $> 60^\circ$ zenith angle (θ)
- ▶ Divided into **three** angular ranges to maximise search efficiency
 - ▶ Down Going Low $\sim 60^\circ-75^\circ$
 - ▶ Down Going High $\sim 75^\circ-90^\circ$
 - ▶ Earth Skimming $\sim 90^\circ-95^\circ$

RECIPE FOR NEUTRINO SHOWER DETECTION WITH THE SD

- ▶ Selecting higher zenith angles (θ)
- ▶ Large Signal Area over Peak (AoP) = $\frac{\text{Integrated Signal}}{\text{Peak}}$
- ▶ AoP ~ 1 , narrow signal (muons)

- ▶ Analysis uses quality cuts to select long signals for an inclined shower
- ▶ Fisher analysis based on AoP and trained on simulations used to obtain high selection efficiency
- ▶ **Dataset:** SD data from 1 January 2004 until 31 December 2021

▶ **No candidate events yet**

[Pierre Auger Coll., JCAP 10 (2019) 022]

[M. Niechciol (Pierre Auger Coll.), PoS (ICRC 2023) 1488]

- ▶ New analysis performed in $\theta \in [60^\circ, 75^\circ]$ (DGL) with electro-magnetic triggers operational since 2014
- ▶ Offer large gain at lower energies with little change in background

Comparison of triggers with ν simulations

$\log_{10}(E/eV) = [17.0, 20.0], \theta \in [60^\circ - 75^\circ]$

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Results after unblinding

$\theta_{rec} \in (67.5^\circ - 70.5^\circ)$

▶ 0 neutrino candidates

- ▶ Auger **most sensitive** to neutrinos slightly below 10^{18} eV
- ▶ Upper-limits have helped **constrain the composition of UHE cosmic rays**

UPPER LIMITS ON NEUTRINO FLUX FOR DIFFUSED AND POINT-LIKE SCENARIOS

- ▶ Auger most sensitive to neutrinos slightly below 10^{18} eV
- ▶ Upper-limits have helped constrain the composition of UHE cosmic rays

- ▶ Only limit at $E_\nu > 10^{17}$ eV
- ▶ Can be used to constrain ν source classes

- ▶ Internal shocks due to shell collision can lead to CR acceleration producing neutrinos (**Prompt** emission)
- ▶ External shocks due to shell collision with ambient material can also lead to CR acceleration (**Afterglow** emission)

Two approaches to model prompt ν emission

Neutrinos from Cosmic Ray Accelerators (NeuCosmA) ApJ, 721, 1538 (2010)	Lia & Tamborra JCAP, 10, 054 (2024)
Only accelerated protons	Includes nuclear cascade
1000 simulations per GRB	Not simulated
Internal Shock (IS) Model	-IS - Photospheric (PH) -Internal-collision-induced magnetic reconnection and turbulence (ICMART)
Uses measured and inferred parameters	Fixed parameters - $\Gamma = 300$ - $t_\nu = 0.5s$

[Y. Lema-Capeans (Pierre Auger Coll.), PoS(ICRC2025)1093]

[T. Paulsen (Pierre Auger Coll.), NuTel 2025]

NeuCosmA approach

$$\phi(E_\nu) = \frac{1}{4\pi} F(E_\nu) 667 \text{ yr}^{-1}$$

▶ Comparable scale to ANTARES at high energies

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Other GRB models

▶ Comparable scale to ANTARES at high energies

▶ Constraining power model dependent

- ▶ Anomalous high energy events observed by ANITA I & III consistent with upward-going air showers

Possible τ decay

- ▶ Energy_{1,2} > 0.2 EeV , Observed zeniths: 117°, 125°
- ▶ Cannot be explained via Standard Model scenarios
- ▶ Could be explained via Beyond Standard Model (BSM) Physics

[B. Yue (Pierre Auger Coll.)]

Sketch not to scale

$$l = \frac{\arctan(-2 \log(L_{\text{down}} / \max\{L_{\text{down}}, L_{\text{up}}\}) / 50)}{\pi/2}$$

$l = 0$ downward favoured
 $l \rightarrow 1$ upward favoured

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- ▶ Could be explained via Beyond Standard Model (BSM) Physics
- ▶ Upward going air showers searched with FD at the Pierre Auger Observatory

- ▶ Auger limits 100(30) times lower than inferred ANITA fluxes for E⁻¹(E⁻²) spectrum for both ANITA I & ANITA III

[Pierre Auger Coll., Phys. Rev. Lett. 134, 121003]

[E. De Vito (Pierre Auger Coll.), PoS (ICRC 2023) 1099]

- ▶ **Assumption:** BSM particle flux interacting with matter at variable cross section produces a τ or ν_τ nearby Earth's surface
The tau lepton propagates into the atmosphere and by its decay produces an upward going shower
- ▶ Search split into three angular bins $[110^\circ, 124.2^\circ]$, $[124.2^\circ, 141.3^\circ]$, $[141.3^\circ, 180^\circ]$
- ▶ Tau generation limit calculated and further converted to BSM limits

[B. Yue(Pierre Auger Coll.), PoS (ICRC 2023) 1095]

Find more in O. Deligny's contribution

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- Several BSM scenarios can be ruled out by the Auger FD and SD

[B. Yue(Pierre Auger Coll.), PoS (ICRC 2023) 1095]

90% C.L.

BSM- ν_τ model

BSM- τ model

$\sigma_{\text{BSM}-\nu_\tau} \rightarrow \infty$: converge with SD-ES- ν_τ limit

[B. Yue (Pierre Auger Coll.)]

- ▶ The Pierre Auger Observatory offers **large exposure to UHE neutrinos**
- ▶ Continues to set **stringent upper limits on the diffuse fluxes** for UHE neutrinos
- ▶ Will continue being an important contributor to **multi messenger astronomy**

- ▶ Can also **constrain different BSM scenario**

- ▶ Other efforts such as optimising the detector further also in progress

- ▶ The deployed **AugerPrime** upgrade can increase the detection capabilities for neutrinos

[ISS Masterclass, Gina Isar: Pierre Auger Coll.]

BACKUP

► Dependence of θ with declination δ

$$\cos\theta(t) = \sin\lambda \sin\delta + \cos\lambda \cos\delta \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T} - \alpha\right)$$

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$$\cos\theta(t) = \sin\lambda \sin\delta + \cos\lambda \cos\delta \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T} - \alpha\right)$$

- ▶ Declination dependent exposure

$$\xi(E_\nu, \delta) = \sum_i \frac{\sigma^{i,\alpha}(E_\nu)^i}{m_N} \int_t \int_X A_{\text{hex}} \cdot \varepsilon(E_\nu, \theta(t), X) \cdot n_{\text{hex}}(t) \cdot dt dX \quad [\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr yr}]$$

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$$\text{Cut Value} = \frac{\log[1.28 \cdot B \cdot \Delta(\mathcal{F})/20] - A}{B}$$

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- ▶ Efficiency represented by total number of neutrino events relative to the previous cut

$$\langle \sigma_{\text{BSM}}^{\text{UHECR}} \rangle = f \cdot \langle \sigma_{\text{SM}}^{\text{UHECR}} \rangle$$

$$\Phi_{\text{BSM}} = f \cdot \Phi_{\text{UHECR}} \quad \text{Not E-2}$$

[Slide from B. Yue (Pierre Auger Coll.)]

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$$\Phi_{\text{BSM}} = f \cdot \Phi_{\text{UHECR}} \quad \text{Not E-2}$$

In general, the SM break should be smaller than the SM, resulting in $f \ll 1$.

Once we the upper limit flux of BSM particles is obtained, $\langle \sigma_{\text{BSM}}^{\text{UHECR}} \rangle$ can be constrained via

$$\langle \sigma_{\text{BSM}}^{\text{UHECR}} \rangle \leq \frac{\Phi_{\text{BSM}}^{\text{C.L.90\%}}}{\Phi_{\text{UHECR}}} \cdot \langle \sigma_{\text{SM}}^{\text{UHECR}} \rangle \quad (6)$$

BSM- ν_τ model

BSM- τ model

[Slide from B. Yue (Pierre Auger Coll.)]

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ANITA-IV solution exclusion

JHEP 07 (2023) 005

- * Diffuse BSM flux (E^{-1}) in (1, 100) EeV
- * Absorption ($\sigma_{\text{BSM-matter}}$) and regeneration are considered
- * Best fit: $\sigma = 8.9 \times 10^{-33} \text{cm}^2$, $\tau = 1.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{s}$ (@1EeV), and $\Phi = 1.8 \text{ km}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$.

[Slide from B. Yue (Pierre Auger Coll.)]